

Perceived Behavioural Control, attitudes and use of mLearning apps among Undergraduate students in a Nigeria University

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Abstract

Background: This study explores the role of mobile learning (mLearning), defined as the use of mobile or wireless devices for learning on the go, as a critical component of Information Technology in tertiary education, specifically within the Faculty of Education at the University of Ibadan.

Method: A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was adopted. The population comprised 2,360 students from first to final year across ten departments in the Faculty of Education. Using a 95% confidence level, a simple random sampling technique selected 333 students. Data were collected via a questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts and percentages.

Findings/Results: The study found that 97.5% (325) of respondents used the Telegram mobile learning app, while 95% (319) used WhatsApp. Additionally, 53.8% (172) strongly agreed they attended classes primarily to meet examination eligibility requirements, and 41.3% (132) strongly agreed they completed assignments independently. Regarding attitudes, 31.6% (101) strongly agreed they used mobile learning platforms only when attendance was mandatory. Perceived behavioural control significantly influenced platform usage.

Implications: The widespread use of social media platforms for mLearning highlights their accessibility but raises concerns about credibility and academic rigor in tertiary education.

Conclusion: Mobile learning platforms, particularly social media apps, are extensively used by students, but their adoption is often driven by mandatory requirements rather than intrinsic motivation, with perceived behavioural control playing a significant role.

Recommendations: Universities should develop institution-specific mobile learning platforms to enhance credibility and reduce reliance on social media for academic purposes, fostering a more structured and reliable mLearning environment.

Key words: Mobile learning (mlearning), Behavioural control and Undergraduate students

Introduction

Rapid proliferation of technology, especially in the context of globalisation has greatly affected our daily lives, either as individuals, groups or societies. Globally, universities are among the first to accept these changes and prepare their students to participate in what can be referred to as the real world of work. The encompassing use of ICTs- particularly the use of the internet has revolutionised and positively altered the design and delivery of educational curricula in universities worldwide. This can be credited to the fact that the incursion of Information Technology (IT) has led to increase in learners' knowledge about computers, consequently increasing their ability to utilise these devices.

Mobile learning (mLearning) can be seen as the use of mobile or wireless devices for the purpose of learning while in transit or on the run. Mobile learning is also a form of e-learning where learning can be done from a distance via a wireless mobile device. Mobile device in this context refers to a computer that is not restricted to a particular fixed environment or space (Alabi, Abass and Igwe, 2020). This technology has become a crucial component of Information Technology in tertiary education. It provides a collection of mobile software applications otherwise known as Apps, which range from education, games, e-books, entertainment and business to lifestyle. Such devices that can be used for mobile learning include cell phones, palmtops, Smartphone and handheld computers (tablet PCs, laptops, and personal media players). In other words, mobile learning is the ability to receive or supply educational contents or materials through electronic devices.

Mobile phones have been improved in recent years to perform many functions such as internet connectivity, sending multimedia messages, information storage, audio and video files display, and so on thereby making learning. Mobile learning devices help students to access learning resources and online courses, anywhere and at any time. It is a widely accepted opinion that in the issue of mobile learning, less stress is involved since most of the devices are quite affordable (even though some are quite expensive) when compared to fixed computers such as desktop Personal Computers and the likelihood of being affected by power failure is low compared to fixed devices. In addition, when we talk of mobile learning, it includes the use of mobile phones majorly, and other hand-held communication devices in performing various academic tasks such as receiving lectures, checking results or making other necessary enquiries.

Mobile learning is an evolving phase of e-learning (electronic learning), as e-learning runs on desktop computers, whereas m-learning depends on mobile devices. It is to be noted that m-learning has the tendency to support all forms of education, even tertiary education is particularly appropriate venue for the integration of student-focused m-learning because mobile devices have become omnipresent on college campuses i.e. they can be found almost everywhere. Diverse mobile learning attempts have been applied in higher education. For example, college students can receive shaping evaluation and feedback from their instructors via a mobile device.

A major form of mobile learning in tertiary education is the use of mobile application (or apps) with programs that give users remote access or can be downloaded onto a mobile device such as tablets or smartphone, and enable users to gain access to resources, interactive features such as games or quizzes that enhance learning or permit communication between users at a distance with the aim of sharing information that are educationally relevant. In other words, mobile learning apps can be a form of mini-software which can be installed in mobile phones or designed web pages which users can access wirelessly and from a distance. Cherednichenko (2021) also described mobile learning applications as softwares designed to be used by learners on devices such as mobile phones or tablets, and that is created using specialised desktop software tools.

A rising number of mobile applications have been made available to students in diverse educational disciplines, including science based courses like Physics, Chemistry, Biology etc. Furthermore, Cherednichenko (2021) classified mobile learning apps into six, namely; online courses such as Coursera and Udemy, mobile and web development services such as Duolingo and Solo learn, memorisation apps such as Brainscape, exam preparation apps such as ExamPrep and Sat Up, supporting tools such as online dictionaries and online libraries. Other examples of mobile learning apps that exist include; Moodle, BioChem Paths, NutriBioChem,

Youtube, Codify, Desmos, Geogebra, Edu Sports, etc. Mobile learning platforms being a technological innovation definitely have some benefits, both for the users and the creators. The common benefits of mobile learning apps to the users as identified by scholars such as and Marinakou and Giousmpasoglou (2015) Praveen and Vasimalaraija (2019) include; ability to learn anywhere and anytime, raised engagement levels, continuous assessment, tested learning strategies, modern pedagogical approach, progress monitoring, social features and daily motivation. For creators or owners of mobile learning apps, Cherednichenko (2021) noted that they derive benefits such as; paid subscriptions, in-app purchases or paid content, increased staff qualifications and opportunity to bring knowledge to people in creative ways. M-learning is still considered to be an option when it comes to selecting learning methods.

In recent times, during Covid-19 where students were asked to be receiving lectures at home through e-learning. Most students were using mobile devices for learning; therefore, the technology has been accepted globally. The technology acceptance model (TAM) and theory of planned behaviour (TPB) has been judged as the widely endorsed model to understand behaviour in applied social psychology. It is one of the most influential and cited models for the predictions of human behavior and technology acceptance. Since it was first introduced over two decades ago, it has been widely used to comprehend and explain behaviour and specific cognitive determinants. Furthermore, TPB is the improved version of theory of reasoned action which includes Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC). PBC deals with situations when people may lack complete volitional control over the behaviour of interest. Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) refers to a person's perception of control over a particular behaviour. In other words, it is an individual's perception of his ability to perform certain behaviours. In his work, PBC may have direct effects on behaviour. Furthermore, Ajzen's (1991) study explores that perceived behavioural control improves intention in relation to positive attitudes and subjective norms. However, Eagly & Chaiken (1993) argue that PBC produces positive intention when an individual forms a positive attitude, but not when an individual form a negative attitude. While previous studies have explored mobile learning platforms of undergraduates, there is limited research on perceived behavioural control among Nigerian undergraduates, which this study seeks to address.

Statement of the problem

The concept of mobile learning is a phenomenon that has been on the rise with the proliferation of handheld ICT device such as smartphones, PDAs, ipads, tablets, etc. In line with the above statement, scholars have attempted to study the implementation of this technological innovation and the relative factors that determine its acceptance and use in various settings and communities. Consequently, many of these scholars

have posited that the concept of mobile learning is still disunited among different stakeholders with diverse national perspectives, difference between academic institutions and industrial organisations. Literature abounds on the use of mobile learning by various levels of stakeholders (such as developers, telecommunication companies, Internet Service Providers (ISPs), students, lecturers, university management, etc.) most especially the academia. Furthermore, extant literature focused on the misuse of mobile learning apps by undergraduate students. However, the attitudes and behaviour of these students might not make them to use mobile learning apps appropriately. It has become absolutely necessary to undertake concentrated studies, examining the use of mobile learning devices and mobile learning apps, as well as the factors that can affect or influence their acceptance and consequent use of mobile learning apps: such factors include perceived behavioural control and attitudes. This research sought to utilise the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) as the underlying research framework to examine the attitude and perceived behavioural control towards using mlearning by undergraduate students of faculty of education, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the various mobile learning apps that is being used by undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan
3. To ascertain the level of perceived behavioural control among undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan.
4. To determine the attitudes of undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan in using mobile learning apps
- 5, To find out the challenges encountered by undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan in using mobile learning apps.

Research questions

1. What are the various mobile learning apps used by undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan?
2. What is the level of perceived behavioural control among undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan?
3. What are the attitudes of undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan in using mobile learning apps?
4. What are the challenges encountered by undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan in using mobile learning platforms?

Literature Review

The concept of mobile learning is a phenomenon that has become increasingly popular over the last two decades, especially in the tertiary stage of education. This is as a

result of rapid technological changes that have occurred in higher education within this time frame. In actual sense, the practical use of this innovation has gone far ahead of the theoretical knowledge, especially in the use of Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs) and the use of applications to support them in mobile devices (Marinakou and Giousmpasoglou, 2015). Tagoe and Abakah (2014) pointed out that the two major components of mobile learning are hardware and networking. They further explained that for an hardware to qualify as mobile technology, such device must be easy to move around and be accessed regularly. The devices that fall into this class are PDAs, MP3 and mobile phones. The 12 second component as noted by Tagoe and Abakah (2014) is wireless network. They further opined that while the devices could operate in a off There are diverse definitions of mobile learning, partially because is a new concept.

Most studies describe mobile learning as an extension of e-learning which is performed using mobile devices such as PDA, mobile phones, laptops etc. (Sad and Goktas, 2013). Park (2011) viewed mobile learning as the use of mobile or wireless devices for the purpose of learning while on the move. These devices include cell phones, smartphones, palmtops, and handheld computers; tablet PCs, laptops, and personal media player (Kukulska-Hulme and Traxler, 2005). While some authors described mobile learning in terms of using mobile devices to undergo learning, others highlight certain characteristics of m-learning including portability through mobile devices, wireless internet connection and omnipresence. For instance, Hoppe et al. (2003 in Iqbal and Qureshi, 2012), define mobile learning as “using mobile devices and wireless transmission”. Kukulska-Hulme and Traxler (2007) suggest that “mobile learning accentuates the ability to enhance the learning process without being glued to a physical location”. Marinakou and Giousmpasoglou (2015) posited that in the tertiary education context, the term mobile learning (m-learning) refers to the use of mobile and handheld devices, such as smart phones, laptops and tablet PCs, in the delivery of teaching and learning. Simply put, m-learning is defined as “the process of learning mediated by a mobile device” (Kearney, Schuck, Burden, and Aubusson, 2012). Leung and Chan (2003) define mobile learning as the point at which mobile computing and electronic learning intersect to produce anytime, anywhere learning experience. Litchfield et al. (2007) define it as the facilitation of learning and access to educational materials for students using mobile devices via a wireless medium.

The use of smart phones currently performs extraordinary functions when it comes to teaching and learning. For instance, students are now able to gain access to their lecture materials remotely and also get spontaneous access to learning management systems where they can meet their urgent information needs (Darko-Adjei, 2019). As a result of this, there has been a sporadic increase in the adoption and implementation of mobile learning all around the world and evidence exist of how developing countries are augmenting their conventional teaching and learning methods with mobile learning

(Tagoe and Abakah, 2014). Darko-Adjei (2019) added that this increase in adoption of mobile learning has particularly improved open or distance education programs offered by tertiary institutions. Pullen, Swabey, Abadoo and Singh (2015) affirmed that most educators and learners have espoused the use of mobile devices for teaching because of its perceived advantages such as readiness, affordability, flexibility, popularity, etc. In addition to this, Sunitha and Elina (2020) conducted a study to find out the various mobile applications used in education, they noted that there are many mobile applications used by students of tertiary institutions when it comes to learning. The various applications used by the respondents as well as the class they belong include: android presentation apps (e.g. Google slides, Power Point, Prezi Viewer), Android Mind Mapping Apps (e.g. Mindomo, Mindmeister, SimpleMind), Android note taking apps (e.g. One note, Google keep, Evenote), Android Video apps (Animoto video maker, Magisto video editor), Android portfolio apps (Three ring, Weebly, Seesaw), Android reference apps (Cite this for me, EasyBib, Mendeley) and Personality development apps (Remente, Elevate, Lumocity, Think up). Quite a number of studies have shown that using mobile applications for learning purposes has the feasibility of allowing most foreign language learners to practice and enhance various language skills on their mobile devices e.g. tablet PCs and smartphones (Shorna and Suchona, 2019). Dang (2013) conducted a study to investigate the attitude and experience of Vietnamese students towards using mobile platforms to learn the English language. The findings of this study exposed that a significant number of students fall back to mobile learning platforms to learn and study English skills. Additionally, it was found that this category of learners expressed very positive and delighting opinions towards making use of this innovation to study English language in the future.

Furthermore, Ababneh (2017) looked into the attitude towards use of mobile learning platforms by foreign language students of the University of Jordan. The study revealed that the participants exhibited a positive attitude towards use of mobile learning platforms in learning foreign language. It was also found that the participants demonstrated a high level of using mobile learning platforms in learning foreign languages outside the classroom as their mean score of using their mobile phones in foreign language learning was 3.85 out of 5 on a Likert-based questionnaire. The conclusion of the study shows that the students would love the teachers as well as curriculum designers to migrate from the 19 traditional curricula to a more technology inclined teaching process. In Nigeria, recent studies such as that of Ifinedo (2017) revealed that there is a fairly high initial acceptance and consequent use of mobile learning platforms by undergraduates 21 even though it is dependent on satisfying factors like perceived self-efficacy, outcome anticipations and perceived support for enhancing social ties. Ajayi, Ayo and Olamide (2019) also examined readiness of accounting students in tertiary institutions to use mobile learning platforms. The study

found that accounting students had a high preference for mobile learning platforms. The study further revealed that more than ninety percent of the respondents utilise mobile learning apps for learning, to search for online resources and to collaborate with colleagues locally. However, slightly above seventy percent of the respondents also indicated that they use mobile learning apps for note taking during lectures, for interactions with tutors and for taking assessments, quizzes and surveys.

Generally, identification of factors that influence students' willingness to accept mobile learning plays a vital role in the design as well as implementation of a mobile learning system that is efficient. Hence, it has become necessary how the concept of perceived behavioural control can influence the willingness to use as well as actual use of mobile learning. Mobile technology affords learners the opportunity to disseminate information and complete coursework even when they are away from their desktop PCs and hard-wired internet connections. This is due to the fact that a wireless device possesses the capability to give instant gratification to students by allowing them to interact with tutors, fellow students, and access course related content from anywhere wireless connectivity is available.

The challenges of the use of mobile learning are many for all stakeholders as it may have many technological restrictions (Marinakou and Giousmpasoglou, 2015). As a matter of fact, Nwaogu and Ozonuwe (2018) affirmed that efforts to leverage mobile technologies for learning are fraught with social, technical, and economic challenges. They noted that the primary social challenge is to be able to convince people that mobile phones are not a barrier to learning, probably due to the intellectually-light and entertainment-heavy content that has been optimized for mobile devices over the past decade. Thus, the high cost of deploying mobile learning technologies prevents developing countries such as Ghana, and even Nigeria from fully implementing mobile learning technology. We can therefore infer that the degree to which students believe that they have the capacity to use mobile devices as well as platforms designed for mobile learning will affect their disposition towards the adoption and use of mobile learning platforms.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The population consists of 2,360 first year to final year students in the ten (10) departments in the faculty of education, University of Ibadan. Faculty of education was purposefully selected because it is one of the largest faculties in University of Ibadan. The sampling technique adopted for this research was simple random sampling technique. Based on the total population of the study, a sample size of 333 out of 2,360 students was selected for the study using 95% confidence level according to Glen (2003)'s sample size. The instrument used for collecting the data from the respondents was a questionnaire. The

questionnaire was validated through experts review and pilot testing with a small sample of students in another department. The questionnaire was divided into six sections, with each section addressing a vital part of the research objectives. The first section collected the demographic information of the respondents, the second section investigated the mobile learning platforms used by the respondents, the third section collected data on the usage level of these platforms by respondents, the fourth section investigated perceived behavioural control of respondents towards the use of mlearning apps, the fifth section investigated the attitudes of students on the use of mobile learning apps by respondents while the last section examined the various challenges faced by respondents in using mobile learning apps. The questionnaire was structured in nature with questions in open and closed ended format. Face and content validity of the instrument was done before administering the instrument. Data were analyzed using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages and the use of SPSS version statistical software.

Findings

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

The distribution of the respondents depicts that 42 (13.1%) of the respondents were from the department of Adult Education, 44 (13.7%) from the department of Arts and Social Science Education, 25 (7.8%) were from department of Counselling and Human Developmental Studies, 8 (2.5%) were from department of Early Childhood Education, 37 (11.5%) were from department of Educational Management, 24 (7.5%) were from department Human Kinetics and Health Education, 107 (33.4%) were from department of Library, Archival and Information Science, 3 (0.9%) were from department of Science and Technology Education, while the remaining 30 (9.4%) were from the department of Special Education. In addition, 119 (37.2%) of the respondents were male while the remaining 201 (62.8%) were female. Furthermore, it shows that 127 (39.7%) of the respondents were aged between 16 and 20, 170 (53.1%) were between the ages of 21 and 25, while the remaining 23 (7.2%) were between the ages of 26 and 30. As regards level of study, 90 (28.1%) of the respondents were first year students, 90 (28.1%) were in 200 level, 93 (29.1%) were in 300 level, while the remaining 47 (14.7%) were final year students.

Table 1: Mobile learning apps being used by undergraduate students

mLearning apps	Yes (%)	No (%)	Number
Moodle	263 (78.9)	70 (21.9)	333
facebook	239 (71.7)	94 (29.4)	333
Youtube	291 (87.3)	42 (13.1)	333
Coursera	103 (30.9)	230 (71.9)	333
Google slides	147 (44.1)	186 (58.1)	333

Whatsapp	319 (95.7)	14 (4.4)	333
Telegram	325 (97.5)	8 (2.5)	333
Mendeley	25 (7.5)	308 (96.2)	333
Google Class	244 (73.2)	89 (27.8)	333
Zoom	282 (88.1)	51 (15.3)	333

Table I sought to find out the various mobile learning apps that have been using for learning purposes by undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan. The findings indicated that 325 (97.5%) of the respondents make use of a mobile learning app called Telegram, while 319 (95.7) use Whatsapp. 239 (71.7%) make use of Facebook as a mobile learning platform, 291 (87.3%) make use of YouTube as a mobile learning platform, just 103 (30.9%) use Coursera platform, The table further indicated that 147 (44.1%) of the respondents make use of Google Slides, 282 (15.3%) use Zoom for learning purposes, 244 (73.2%) make use of Google Class, 319 (95.7%) use WhatsApp for learning, The implication of this finding is that students preferred telegram and Whatsapp as most mobile learning apps, which aligns with the hypothesis that perceived ease of use influences platform adoption.

Table 2: What is the degree of perceived behavioural control among undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan?

Statements	SD (%)	D (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
I attend classes to increase my chances of being eligible for examinations	11 (3.4)	27 (8.4)	110 (34.4)	172 (53.8)
I am capable of learning individually without assistance from my colleagues	8 (2.5)	55 (17.2)	146 (45.6)	111 (34.7)
I search for learning materials without waiting for the lecturer to tell me	12 (3.8)	43 (13.4)	173 (54.1)	92 (28.8)
I read ahead of classes and do extra reading after classes	13 (4.1)	68 (21.3)	179 (55.9)	60 (18.8)
I do assignments on my own without depending on friends and classmates	7 (2.2)	30 (9.4)	151 (47.2)	132 (41.3)
I need a lot of illustrations before I can understand a concept	17 (5.3)	122 (38.1)	110 (34.4)	71 (22.2)

I wait for the lecturer to explain a topic before I can read about it	21	124	113	62
	(6.6)	(38.8)	(35.3)	(19.4)
I don't feel comfortable in class if I am not familiar with the topic being taught	34	101	118	67
	(10.6)	(31.6)	(36.9)	(20.9)
I read only when tests or examinations are approaching	37	126	100	57
	(11.6)	(39.4)	(31.3)	(17.8)
I still need more explanations after reading before I can understand a topic	25	112	111	72
	(7.8)	(35.0)	(34.7)	(22.5)

Table 2 indicated that 172 (53.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they only attend classes to increase their chances of being eligible for examinations, Also, the table shows that 111 (53.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they are capable of learning on their own without any assistance from their colleague inferred from the table that 92 (28.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they search for learning materials on their own without waiting for the course lecturer to direct them to do so. Furthermore, the data presented suggests that 60 (18.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they read ahead of classes and do extra reading after classes, The table further depicts that 132 (41.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they do their assignments on their own without depending on friends and classmates, The data presented also indicates that 71 (22.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they need a lot of illustrations before they can understand a new concept. This implies that students could control their behaviours and that they remember of sons or daughters of whom they are by reading and do assignments on their own.

Table 3: What are the attitudes of undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan in using mobile learning apps?

Statements	SD %	D %	A %	SA %
I use mobile learning platforms only if attendance is compulsory	20 (6.3)	110 (34.4)	89 (27.8)	101 (31.6)
I can use mobile learning apps without assistance from colleagues	4 (1.3)	21 (6.6)	138 (43.1)	157 (49.1)
I make use of Mobile Learning Platforms without waiting for the lecturer to tell me	10 (3.1)	64 (20)	154 (48.1)	92 (28.8)
I make use of Mobile Learning Platforms to do my assignments without friends and classmates	6 (1.9)	34 (10.6)	146 (45.6)	134 (41.9)
I need a lot of illustrations on how to use Mobile Learning Platforms	33 (10.3)	132 (41.3)	96 (30)	58 (18.4)
I wait for the lecturer to recommend resources on Mobile Learning Platforms	20 (6.3)	109 (34.1)	118 (36.9)	73 (22.8)
I do not feel comfortable using Mobile Learning Platforms	56 (17.5)	134 (41.9)	82 (25.6)	48 (15)
I use Mobile Learning Platforms when tests or examinations are close	37 (11.6)	138 (43.1)	82 (25.6)	63 (19.7)
I use Mobile Learning Platforms if it is user-friendly	19 (5.9)	74 (23.1)	143 (44.7)	84 (26.3)
I use Mobile Learning if I have the required devices for it	20 (6.3)	55 (17.2)	169 (52.8)	76 (23.8)

Table 3 depicts that 101 (31.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they use mobile learning platforms only if the attendance on such platforms is made compulsory. Also, the table shows that 157 (49.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they make use of mobile learning platforms on their own without any assistance from their colleagues, it can be inferred from the table that 92 (28.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they search for learning materials on mobile learning platforms without waiting for the course lecturer to direct them to do so. Furthermore, the table suggests that 134 (41.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they make use of mobile learning to do their assignments on their own without depending on friends and classmates. The data presented also indicates that 59 (18.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they need a lot of illustrations on how to use mobile learning platforms before they can use them, It can also be inferred from the table that 73 (22.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that they wait for the lecturer

recommend learning. This finding implies that the high usage of general mobile platforms indicates that these platforms are preferred by students for learning.

Table 4: challenges encountered by undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan in using mobile learning apps.

Challenges	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
Mobile Learning Platforms make me isolated from my colleagues	73 (22.8)	70 (21.9)	147 (45.9)	30 (9.4)
Mobile Learning Platforms make learning boring for me	70 (21.9)	90 (28.1)	125 (29.1)	35 (10.9)
I am not tech savvy so I am not confident to use mobile learning apps	45 (14.1)	73 (22.8)	146 (45.6)	56 (17.5)
My phone configuration makes the apps difficult to use	32 (10)	89 (27.8)	149 (46.6)	50 (15.6)
Poor internet access	103 (32.2)	149 (46.6)	55 (17.2)	13 (4.1)
Low bandwidth in the school premises	89 (27.8)	140 (43.8)	80 (25)	11 (3.4)
I get distracted easily when using mobile learning apps	79 (24.7)	140 (43.8)	85 (26.6)	16 (5)
Inadequate electricity supply	120 (37.5)	146 (45.6)	43 (13.4)	11 (3.4)
Short battery lifespan of mobile phone	97 (30.3)	143 (44.7)	64 (20)	16 (5)
Inability to multitask	67	104	111	38

The presented data depicts that 73 (22.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed that mobile learning platforms make them feel isolated from their colleagues,. Similarly, the table also indicates that, 70 (21.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed that mobile learning platforms make learning boring for them. In addition, the table shows that 45 (14.1%) strongly agreed that they are not confident using mobile learning platforms because they are not tech savvy, 73 (22.8%) agreed, 125 (29.1%) disagreed, while 35 (10.9%) strongly disagreed. Furthermore, the table reveals that 32 (10%) of the respondents strongly agreed that their phone configuration makes it difficult for them to use mobile learning apps.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of this study has shown that the use of mobile learning platforms among undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan is high, although not all

the mobile learning platforms are being used by them. However, the level of usage of common mobile learning platforms such as Facebook, Zoom, WhatsApp, Telegram and YouTube is very high as more than eighty percent of the respondents affirmed that they use these platforms and that they do so frequently. This slightly corroborates the submission of Ifinedo (2017) that acceptance and consequent use of mobile learning platforms by Nigerian undergraduates is fairly high. This is also in accordance with the findings of Ajayi, Ayo and Olamide (2019) who submitted that the preference for mobile learning applications among accounting students in Nigerian tertiary institutions is high as these students use these apps for learning, collaboration and searching for learning resources. The implication is that students admits acceptance of mobile learning platforms for reading and that the high usage of WhatsApp and Telegram indicates that these platforms are preferred by students, which aligns with the hypothesis that perceived ease of use influences platform adoption.

The study also revealed that the respondents are capable of doing their assignments without assistance from their friends or course mates; they are also capable of searching for learning materials and reading ahead of classes without being necessarily told by the lecturer. This connotes that the level to which undergraduates of faculty of education, University of Ibadan believe that they are capable of controlling their learning behaviour is high. This is in tandem with the submission of Yzer (2012) that people will accept that they are capable of executing a particular behaviour when they believe that they have the resources and opportunities to perform the behaviour and when they believe that they can freely make decisions to use those resources and opportunities.

This agrees with the assertion of Cheon et al. (2012) that college students' behavioural control was a major influence on their intention to use mobile learning platforms. This also supports the findings of Yang (2012) that students who possessed a high mobile self-efficacy demonstrated a positive attitude towards the use of mobile learning applications.

The findings of this study also revealed that undergraduates of faculty of education, university of Ibadan encounter certain challenges in their use of mobile learning platforms. These challenges range from personal, to financial and even infrastructural challenges. For instance, most of the respondents opined that they find it difficult to use mobile learning platforms because of poor internet access, low bandwidth in their campuses, inadequate electricity supply and short battery lifespan of their mobile phones. This is in tandem with the findings of Sarrab et al. (2013) that some of the challenges and restrictions to the use of mobile learning include; lack of standardization, low bandwidth, poor internet access, the limited processor speed and small screen size, low storage and short battery life. It also gives credence to the

assertion of Park (2011) that the usability problems of mobile phones can serve as limitations to using mobile learning platforms.

Conclusion

Use of mobile learning platforms has been on the increase since the advent of the Internet and social media. This connotes that more universities as well as their students are beginning to take advantage of mobile learning platforms to increase their learning potential as well as the quality of education being offered. This innovation is however, more common in the developed countries like UK and US where a good number of their universities have built an institutionalised mobile learning platform.

In Africa and Nigeria by extension, most universities do not have an institutionalised mobile learning platform of their own, but they make use of the open platforms developed by foreign universities and some mobile applications or software designed for such purpose. Therefore, the most commonly used mobile learning platforms among undergraduates in Nigeria are mobile software such as Zoom, Telegram and Edmodo. To complement these applications, popular social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp and YouTube have been adopted as mobile learning platforms due to their multipurpose nature. Like many other innovations, use of mobile learning platforms has been found to be influenced by different user behaviour. This study was able to establish that perceived behavioural control significantly affects the use of mobile learning platforms.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made to facilitate the effective use of mobile learning platforms;

1. The university management should put adequate technical infrastructures such as internet connectivity, electricity supply and high bandwidth.
2. Lecturers should moderate the use of social learning platforms in a more interactive manner.
3. Universities should endeavour to have an institution mobile learning platforms as
4. Against the adoption of social media platforms for learning purpose as this will lead to increased credibility
5. Developers of mobile learning platforms should make the platforms more suitable for smaller mobile operating systems such as Android and IOS.

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